

Synthetic Ethnicity Alteration for Diversifying Face Datasets - Investigating Recognition and Quality

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Abstract—The rapid advancement of biometric authentication requires extensive performance tests to inhibit the discriminatory treatment of travellers due to their demographic background. However, the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) restricts the use of face images collected as part of border controls to be processed for no reason other than their original purpose. In this work, we explore altering the ethnicity using synthetic face image generation approaches to increase the diversity of datasets to represent multiple ethnicities of the same identity. In this work, we present a systematic study to assess the applicability of ethnicity alteration of face images by studying the performance of the face recognition system (FRS) and face image quality assessment (FIQA). Ethnicity-altered images were generated using Generative Adversarial Network-based (GAN) image-to-image translation and manifold learning models. We test these approaches on a publicly available Racial Faces in the Wild (RFW) dataset and focus on Asian, Black, and Indian ethnicity. We conduct experiments to benchmark the ethnicity-altered images for FRS performance using two recent deep learning models and complement it with FIQA analysis using three different algorithms. With the limited drop in FRS performance and a similar effect on quality scores, our results indicate the applicability of ethnicity alteration to diversify the datasets and make systems fair.

Index Terms—Synthetic Data, Face Image Quality Assessment, Face Recognition, Ethnicity Alteration, Ethnicity Alteration, Generative Adversarial Networks

I. INTRODUCTION

The deployment of face recognition systems has gained popularity in various application scenarios, such as border control initiatives like the European Entry-Exit System (EES) [1]. In particular, the EES will be used as a central system for collecting and verifying biometric data of travelers to the Schengen area (29 European countries) at all border crossing points to facilitate the cooperation of visa and law enforcement agencies. The biometric performance of systems deployed in such sensitive environments must comply with high standards, such as those defined in the best practices for automated border control of the European Border and Coast Guard authorities [2]. At the same time, the European General Data Protection Law complicates the processing of biometric data to avoid privacy leakages [3], which classifies biometrics data as personal data; thus, its storage and processing require

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Indian Real	Synthetic	Black	Asian
CRFIQA: 2.28	CRFIQA: 2.30	CRFIQA: 2.20	CRFIQA: 1.58
MagFace: 31.16	MagFace: 31.15	MagFace: 22.36	MagFace: 22.36
SEFIQA:0.885	SEFIQA:0.885	SEFIQA:0.890	SEFIQA:0.882
EF. Arc+: 96.49	EF. Arc+: 96.49	EF. Arc+: 44.83	EF. Arc+: 39.18
EF. Cos+: 96.40	EF. Cos+: 96.40	EF. Cos+: 41.98	EF. Cos+: 37.40

Fig. 1: Example of ethnicity altered real (red box) and synthetic (blue box) face image annotated with FRS comparison scores and FIQA metrics.

the individual’s consent and underlie strict legal restrictions. Therefore, compliance with such regulations is required, especially when data is collected on the unstructured web and is widely distributed. Recent research trends propose using synthetic data as an alternative to authentic data to comply with privacy regulations and ensure future FRS research. Inspired by the recent success of generating realistic synthetic data for computer vision tasks using Conditional Generative Adversarial Networks (cGAN) [4], a new research area of biometric research emerges to leverage this technique for creating ethnicity-altered synthetic faces of the same individual. The dependability of face recognition frameworks is subject to consistent accuracy across different ethnicities and face image quality. This property is crucial in the European Entry-Exit System, passport issuance, and civilian ID management [1]. The disparity and the bias of FRS towards certain ethnicities, skin tones, and genders underscores a significant gap between the overall performance of these systems and their ability to generalize to more complex scenarios and sub-problems [5]. Further, the performance of face recognition systems depends on the quality of the images presented to them. Reference face images of higher quality are expected to support better recognition performance, and poor-quality images can degrade the performance of these systems on all tasks. While the value of real and sufficiently representative biometric data for biometric performance tests is obvious, it is becoming common to use in training and evaluation synthetic biometric data samples representing comparable properties to real data.

Controlling and assessing the quality of such synthetically generated biometric data can be used to train better FRS models and develop robust Face Image Quality Assessment (FIQA) algorithms while respecting the privacy regulations imposed by various national and international regulations [6]. Further, the synthetic data should represent different ethnicities to make the systems fair and robust [7]. With such motivation, we explore a synthetic face generation scheme to diversify given face datasets to alter the ethnicity and skin tone in the synthetic data. However, such data can be used if the utility in biometrics can be established by looking at two aspects: (i) utility in terms of performance of the FRS and (ii) measuring the representativeness of its quality compared to real biometric data of face. An example of FIQA estimated using various approaches is depicted in Fig 1 to give the reader an idea of varying quality scores of real and synthetic ethnicity-altered images. We motivate this work to systematically study and understand the influence of such synthetically altered images in FRS performance evaluation and FIQA, resulting in the following contributions.

- We employ a balanced face image dataset representing three ethnicities (Asian, Black, and Indian) where the ethnicities are altered using Generative Adversarial Network-based (GAN) image-to-image translation and manifold learning models. The data consists of 15,000 real samples of Asian, Black, and Indian ethnicities used for training the ethnicity alteration models. Our performance evaluation analysis is done on an independent Racial Faces in-the Wild (RFW) [8] in a truly unknown data setting to indicate the significance of all study aspects.
- We then measure the performance of such data in FRS using two recent deep learning-based FRS models (ElasticFace Arc+ and ElasticFace Cos+ [9]) to establish the use of synthetic ethnicity alteration as an alternative to using real data from different ethnicities.
- Further, we measure the biometric sample utility of the ethnicity-altered samples using three state-of-the-art deep learning-based FIQA methods such as CR-FIQA [10], MagFace [11]/OFIQ¹, and SER-FIQ [12].
- We also demonstrate the utility of the synthetic ethnicity alteration approaches in FRS using the Error-vs-Discard Characteristics (EDC) analysis to present the results that closely resemble the real data, indicating utility and applicability in FRS for various purposes.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II reviews related works, Section III discusses the details of the newly created racial balance, publicly available test datasets, and presents a qualitative study on ethnicity dataset of Asian, Black, and Indian subjects. Section IV presents the investigation methodology, Section V presents the quality evaluation using CycleGAN, StarGAN, and FGAN. Section VI further presents a quantitative analysis using FRS and FIQA, and Section VII concludes the paper.

¹OFIQ-report: https://github.com/BSI-OFIQ/OFIQ-Project/blob/main/doc/reports/Public_Report_V1.1_2024_09_30.pdf

II. RELATED WORK

We present a brief background work needed to comprehend our work in the following section without delving into details.

A. Face Ethnicity Alteration

Generative Adversarial Networks based on altering facial attributes have been well explored using various approaches that rely on image-to-image translation and manifold learning. For instance, CycleGANs [13] and StarGAN [14] use image-to-image translation. FGAN [15] on the other hand uses a manifold learning-based approach to alter the attributes. We base our work on using these approaches to generate a synthetic dataset for altering the ethnicity. We refrain from detailing the approaches for simplicity and refer the readers to [13]–[15] for details on architecture. However, we provide the necessary details of training and testing datasets generated using these approaches in Section III for the better understanding of our analysis.

III. DATASET

We present a brief overview of the datasets used in this work. We use an in-house balanced dataset (Ethnicity Alteration Training (EAT) Dataset) representing three ethnicities to train the ethnicity alteration models, and then a separate testing dataset is used to report the performance, as presented below.

Fig. 2: Sample images from in-house EAT dataset illustrating three different ethnicities.

A. Face Image Quality

Face Image Quality Assessment (FIQA) algorithms typically generate a quality score between [0, 100] to indicate quality where 0 represents a low quality, and 100 is a high-quality score [16], [17]. ISO/IEC 39794-5 [6] and ICAO 9303 [18] enforce a set of quality measures that can be at the component and image levels. The main intuition of estimating the quality is to predict the utility of the image for a FRS model when the ethnicity is synthetically altered by providing additional quality information that can then be used to reject low-quality face samples during synthetic dataset generation. A high-quality score is expected to result in a high FRS score, and vice-versa [19], and the utility of face images across different quality can be further measured through an Error versus Discard Characteristic (EDC) analysis

[19]. Several recent works have explored deep learning models to measure the quality of the image for biometric applications. An unsupervised learning-based SER-FIQ [12] measures the image quality specific to the face recognition model without requiring any ground truth quality score. Supervised learning-based MagFace [11] integrates FIQA within the FRS. Another supervised learning-based CR-FIQA [10] estimates the quality of a facial image by predicting its relative classifiability based on the location of the feature representation in the angular space concerning its class center and the nearest negative-class center. We choose these three approaches to measure the utility of ethnicity-altered images.

B. Ethnicity Alteration Training (EAT) Dataset

Noting the limited availability of datasets to train ethnicity alteration, we use an in-house dataset with 15000 images from three different ethnicities (Asian, Black, and Indian). The in-house dataset makes use of publicly and privately available CACD [20], FFHQ [21], Celeba [22], AgeDB [23], MORPH [24], CASIA [25], ICD [26], ECLF [27], and Maga Asia [28]. All images were processed using MTCNN [29] for face detection and further cropped, aligned, and resized to 128×128 pixels. Further, we curated the dataset to retain 15,000 images from Asian, Black, and Indian ethnicities based on the ground truth annotated with DeepFace [30] and manually verifying them. We use this dataset to train both image-to-image translation and manifold-based models to create synthetic data from one ethnicity to another in an ethnicity-paired manner.

C. Testing Dataset - Racial Faces in-the Wild

To evaluate the performance with FRS and FIQA, we employ the Racial Faces in the Wild (RFW) [8]. While this dataset contains four testing subsets such as Caucasian, Asian, Indian, and African/Black, each comprising approximately 10K images of 3K individuals, we choose three ethnicities alone (i.e., Asian, Indian, and Black) to be consistent in our findings. The testing dataset is further processed to remove the images with severe occlusion and poses by measuring the magnitude of embeddings in MagFace [11]. The images with a lower magnitude of embedding were eliminated to create the testing dataset with the following distribution - Asian (1240/3579 subjects/images), Black (1386/3513), and Indian (1277/3279) ethnicities. These images were further used to alter the ethnicities from Asian \rightarrow Black, Asian \rightarrow Indian, Indian \rightarrow Black, Indian \rightarrow Asian, Black \rightarrow Asian and Black \rightarrow Indian using the models trained on the EAT dataset.

IV. INVESTIGATIONS METHODOLOGY

The primary objective of this study was to investigate the impact of ethnicity changes on FRS for the same individuals. To accomplish this, a well-structured and balanced dataset (EAT) (detailed in Section III) was created representing three distinct ethnic groups (Asian, Black, and Indian). The GAN-based models were trained to alter the ethnicities using six different combinations: Asian \rightarrow Black ($A \rightarrow B$), Asian \rightarrow

Fig. 3: Samples of the dataset used in this work presenting the ethnicity alteration of Asian.

Indian ($A \rightarrow I$), Black \rightarrow Asian ($B \rightarrow A$), Black \rightarrow Indian ($B \rightarrow I$), Indian \rightarrow Asian ($I \rightarrow A$), and Indian \rightarrow Black ($I \rightarrow B$). The trained models were applied to the RFW [8] dataset to perform the ethnicity transformations. To assess the effects of ethnicity alterations on FRS, two pre-trained deep FRS models (Elastic Arc+, and Elastic Cos+) were employed. We further analyze the FRS and FIQA using Error-vs-Discard characteristic (EDC) analysis to measure the suitability of ethnicity-altered image quality. The results were measured using three complementary metrics: (i) face image quality assessment, (ii) cross-ethnicity face verification performance, (iii) joint evaluation of FRS and FIQA.

Fig. 4: Samples of the dataset used in this work presenting the ethnicity alteration.

V. QUALITY EVALUATION

In this section, we present a series of quantitative comparisons to provide readers with a comprehensive understanding of ethnicity alteration based on our findings.

Fig. 5: Samples of the dataset used in this work presenting the ethnicity alteration of Indian

A. Asian \rightarrow (Black, Indian)

Fig 3 illustrates ethnicity-altered images transitioning from Asian to Black and Indian ethnicity. We can observe that CycleGAN, StarGAN, and FGAN models execute structural changes in the eyes, lip shape, and facial color characteristics of Black and Indian ethnicity. All models generated realistic

images with ethnicity altered from the original ethnicity. Furthermore, Asian skin tones generally range from light to medium. Black individuals often have darker skin tones, and Indian skin tones vary widely from very light to dark brown, as shown in Fig 3.

B. Black \rightarrow (Asian, Indian)

Fig 4 demonstrates that all models can effectively translate images from Black to Indian ethnicity and thin the eyebrows. Indian ethnic groups, in contrast to Asians, commonly exhibit prominent eyelids, well-defined nasal bridges with tip projection, and relatively darker and more uneven skin tones. Further, Black individuals rounded eyes change to almond-shape in Asians.

C. Indian \rightarrow (Asian, Black)

We can observe that the eyes have been narrowed, the skin tones have adjusted according to ethnicity, and the eyelids, set on a more prominently exposed platform, feature a well-defined nasal bridge with tip projection and relatively darker and more uneven skin tones when transitioning from Indian to Asian or Black ethnicity. Additionally, Asian groups tend to exhibit wider intercanthal widths and smaller eye openings, which are notably distinct in ethnicity-altered faces.

Fig. 6: illustrates face image quality score distribution comparison with CycleGAN (row1), StarGAN (row2), and FGAN (row3) by SER-FIQ model.

VI. QUANTITATIVE EVALUATION

To assess the suitability of ethnicity-altered images using image-to-image translation and manifold models, we first conduct FIQA performance analysis to verify the resemblance of the quality of ethnicity-altered images compared to images representing real ethnicity using FIQA assessment. We demonstrate the performance of these images for FRS by presenting

the biometric performance results using a cross-ethnicity face verification protocol, as detailed below. We further perform a joint evaluation of FIQA and FRS using EDC plot.

Fig. 7: Face image quality score distribution comparison with CycleGAN (row1), StarGAN (row2), and FGAN (row3) by CRFIQA.

A. Face Image Quality Assessment

We employ three state-of-the-art FIQA models such as CR-FIQA [10], MagFace [11], and SER-FIQ [12] to assess the quality of ethnicity altered images. We selected 500 occlusion-free, frontal pose, and uniform illuminated images of each ethnicity from the RFW test dataset for assessing the FIQA measures. Similarly, we select a set of ethnicity-altered images to compare against. We present the kernel density distribution analysis to demonstrate the quality score distribution across real and ethnicity-altered images.

As shown in Fig 6, a high degree of overlap in the quality score distribution for SER-FIQ suggests no significant quality difference across real and ethnicity-altered images. A consistent observation can be noted for ethnicity alteration across different sets (i.e., Asian to Black, Indian).

We also provide kernel density distribution analysis for CR-FIQA and MagFace-based quality estimates in Fig 7 and 8. As we can see, the SER-FIQ model on CycleGAN quality distribution of ethnicity altered, generated, and input images quality score distributions exhibit a relatively similar shape with huge overlapping areas. SER-FIQ is the most convincing quality estimation approach for Indian and Asian ethnicity. While CR-FIQA performs better on Black Ethnicity.

B. Cross Ethnicity Face Verification

We employ a cross-ethnicity verification protocol to assess face verification performance when the ethnicity is altered. We use the image of a subject representing original ethnicity as the enrolment sample and the image with altered ethnicity as

Fig. 8: Face quality score distribution comparison with CycleGAN (row1), StarGAN (row2), and FGAN (row3) by MagFace/OFIQ.

the probe sample. We use a recent pre-trained FRS model - ElasticFace [9] to extract the embeddings and compute the distance using simple cosine distance. A higher score from the comparison indicates the persistence of identity across ethnicity.

We thoroughly evaluated the Face Recognition System (FRS) on the Race Fairness in the Wild (RFW) test datasets by creating genuine and impostor image pairs (protocol). To create genuine pairs, we utilized the generated images of each target domain and the input images of the source domain ethnicity for individual subjects. Furthermore, we randomly generated cross-subject imposter (negative) pairs for comparison. The results of the state-of-the-art FRS evaluation are presented in Table I and illustrate the system’s performance at the False Non-Match Rate (FNMR) with a False Match Rate (FMR) of 0.01%. We note that the performance of real data for a particular ethnicity is comparable to that of ethnicity-altered data. We note a slight drop in performance in the cross-ethnicity verification protocol. It can be noticed that CycleGAN and StarGAN verification rates are lower than FGAN due to the latter generating better ethnicity-altered images (as seen in Fig 3, Fig 4, and Fig 5). Also, altered Asian and Black images using CycleGAN exhibit minor differences in verification accuracy compared to real and cross-ethnicity altered images. Additionally, altered Indian ethnicity images using StarGAN demonstrate better verification accuracy than those altered using CycleGAN, suggesting that these models are more effective for generating cross-altered ethnicity synthetic datasets. On average, all facial recognition systems perform better for Indian ethnicity than Asian and Black ethnicity across real and altered images.

C. Joint Evaluation of FRS and FIQA

We further evaluate the utility of synthetically altered images by studying the EDC to verify the image quality usable within FRS. EDC curve shows the verification error rate on the y-axis achieved when discarding a certain percentage of face images (x-axis). Based on the predicted quality values, these discarded images have the lowest predicted quality, and the error rate is calculated on the remaining face images. The EDC curve indicates good quality estimation when the verification error decreases consistently and the ratio of unconsidered images increases. We employ the Arcface FRS [31] described to measure the errors vs discard characteristics. The verification error is reported regarding the false non-match rate (FNMR) at false match rates (FMR). The FMR is reported at a fixed 0.05% FMR threshold. The best-performing CycleGAN model results is shown in Fig 9.

Fig. 9: EDC plot depicting the performance evaluation of ArcFace on CR-FIQA, MagFace, and SER-FIQ with CycleGAN.

VII. CONCLUSION

Due to ethical, legal, and privacy concerns, the exchange, processing, and storing of biometric samples such as face images with private information, has become a challenging technical and legal issue. In this work, we have focused on altering the ethnicity using image-to-image translation and manifold-based approaches. A detailed study of FRS and FIQA supports using ethnicity alteration schemes to diversify the training data for biometric purposes. The training on the in-house dataset and testing on a public dataset further support our idea of using it in the real-world application context. The analysis further provides an advantage of using such data for large-scale training of fair systems without the explicit need for multi-ethnicity datasets, reducing the tedious manual labour and privacy-compliant solutions. The dataset can be used to create and evaluate biometric systems for fairness. Future works can extend this to increase the resolution of images and diversify the data with other ethnicities.

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TABLE I: Cross ethnicity face verification rate (%) of FRS on Asian (Mated comparisons:11,443, Non-mated comparisons:14305), Black (Mated comparisons:10,195, Non-mated comparisons:15,036), and Indian (Mated comparisons:10,143, Non-mated comparisons:13,097). FNMR is evaluated at FMR threshold for SOTA FRS.

FRS	FNMR@FMR=0.01%						
	Real	CyleGAN	StarGAN	FGAN	CyleGAN	StarGAN	FGAN
	Asian	Asian \leftrightarrow Black			Asian \leftrightarrow Indian		
FaceNet	49.49	30.60	11.89	27.28	42.14	18.19	30.60
PFE	45.87	82.76	55.06	95.46	93.63	67.35	93.42
Elastic Arc+	99.77	88.84	57.04	99.42	88.84	84.34	98.54
Elastic Cos+	99.87	90.77	59.93	98.75	97.86	71.30	99.44
	Black	Black \leftrightarrow Asian			Black \leftrightarrow Indian		
FaceNet	45.87	23.16	12.66	60.86	17.57	15.85	45.88
PFE	99.51	95.48	57.81	98.99	85.70	64.34	97.61
Elastic Arc+	99.87	98.12	67.03	99.82	87.48	55.57	95.81
Elastic Cos+	99.80	90.83	75.13	99.86	93.15	81.21	98.64
	Indian	Indian \leftrightarrow Black			Indian \leftrightarrow Asian		
FaceNet	57.44	41.05	24.50	68.79	52.46	28.06	51.80
PFE	99.42	91.04	87.41	99.02	99.79	81.03	97.57
Elastic Arc+	99.79	90.16	85.58	99.61	90.83	87.04	99.70
Elastic Cos+	99.83	91.11	92.22	99.66	88.84	82.22	99.66

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